

Title: A Valuation Based Theory of Learning's Origin and Development

Authors: Vincent B. Moneymaker

¹ Self-Employed, 914 E. Elm Street, Brea, CA 92821

5 *Corresponding author. E-mail: vbmoneymaker@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0002-8787-4319

10 **Abstract:** This paper hypothesizes that learning occurs thru sleep, and all animals that sleep possess at least one of two dynamic information valuation mechanisms. The first are the sensations of pain and pleasure, while the second are emotions which evolved from pain and pleasure. These dynamic valuation mechanisms are a critical cognitive development because they enable animals, from the simplest to the most complex, to learn from their environments. They do so by marking valuable memories for long-term storage during sleep while also enabling their recall when an animal awakes.

15 **Summary:**

The fundamental sensations of pain and pleasure evolved as the most basic dynamic information valuation mechanism in the earliest animals with neuron-like structures. Emotions then evolved from pain and pleasure as a more nuanced valuation mechanism in animals possessing specialized emotion-generating structures.

20 The purpose of these related information valuation mechanisms is to mark important memories for retention during sleep so that learning can occur. As such, the base feelings of pain and pleasure should be viewed as cognitively dependent sensations (just as emotions

are) rather than as physical sensations. Which means they will be present in any species capable of learning, including species lacking neurons but possessing neuron-like structures, like sponges. Furthermore, all species capable of learning will be found to engage in some form of sleep because this is the process by which animals identify valuable memories in order to learn from them.

As to emotions, it is submitted they are a ubiquitous feature of the brains of all higher-order animals, including mammals, birds, reptiles, and perhaps even fish and other classes of animals, such as cephalopods. The reason they'll likely be found in all species possessing advanced cognitive structures, such as the amygdala, is they are the key neural development that enabled species to begin making more nuanced information valuations, which, in turn, led to the evolution of more complex cognitive abilities

Lastly, regarding the dreaming stage of sleep, it is hypothesized that it is critical to learning because it is the process by which newly stored memories are recalled so that their value can be accurately measured and assessed. As such, the purpose of dreaming is to refine learning that is the product of newly stored memories.

Main Text:

I. The Fundamental Nature of Learning

To explain the origin of learning, one must first define it. Learning is thus the ability to
5 make information valuation determinations. And it is the product of three mechanisms working
together, which are:

1. Storage
2. Information valuation
3. Selective retention and recall

10 So, in neural-based species, storage takes place via neurons or neuron-like structures. In
turn, and as will be discussed hereafter, information valuation takes place via the sensations of
pain and pleasure and, in more cognitively complex animals, emotions. Finally, the selective
retention of valuable memories occurs via sleep, with pain and pleasure and emotions then
guiding behaviour once animals awake.

15 As to the importance of learning, it is one of the three principal capabilities animal
species must possess in order to survive, with the other two being eating and procreating. We
know how animals eat and procreate, but our understanding of how they learn is far from
complete.¹ Of the three, learning is the most important because it effectively enables the other
two. As a result, animals that are unable to learn over time have little to no chance of eating on
20 their own, much less procreating, which guarantees they will not survive.

In proposing the within theory regarding how animals learn, this paper asserts that Albert
Einstein's principle of equivalence should be extended to biological processes.² The point of this
theoretical extension is that similar behaviours observed across a variety of species with a
common genetic background will almost certainly be a product of the same underlying biological
25 mechanisms.

Furthermore, the more widely a behaviour or biological process appears in nature, the more fundamental it will be to the survival of species possessing it. As such, the equivalence principle should be used as a benchmark for determining how important particular behaviors or processes are to a species' survival.

5 Applying this principle to sleep, its practically ubiquitous occurrence among animals points to it being as necessary to species' survival as eating and procreating are.³ So, given its fundamental nature, sleep, by process of elimination, is almost certainly involved in and responsible for learning. Which is the one crucial survival activity that still remains largely unexplained.⁴

10 In applying the principle of equivalence to animals, this paper proposes that all animals with neurons or neuron-like structures sleep because that is the process by which they learn. Specifically, and as highlighted before, this process involves animals using two different information valuation mechanisms to mark memories they generate while they're awake. The first and more basic information valuation mechanism is that of pain and pleasure, which is
15 present in all animals that are able to learn. The second, later evolved mechanism is that of emotions, which are present in animals with more complex neural frameworks that possess specialized emotion-generating structures, such as the amygdala.

 During sleep, the strength of memories' sensory and emotion tags signal to an animal's learning network (be it a brain in some cases, a nerve net in others, or neuron-like structures in
20 the oldest evolved creatures) as to which memories to keep and which to disregard. Then, when an animal awakes, the process begins again. The memory portion of its learning network, of which some part has been reset during sleep, is freed up to take in new sensory and emotion-marked memories. As part of a feedback loop, previously stored high-value memories are then

recalled in order to guide behaviour while also aiding in the generation of new memories. The result is animals are able to learn in a continuously adaptive way.

Ultimately, this is how animals store information that is important for their survival but is too complex or variable to be inherited by genetic means. And simplified to its essence, this is how all animals with neurons or neuron-like structures learn.

II. The Mental Trade-off Justifying the Inherent Danger of Sleep

Sleep's fundamental role in learning explains why this seemingly maladaptive behavior is seen in practically all animals, even though its associated state of external unconsciousness (or lethargy in the case of animals with simpler neural networks) subjects its practitioners to extended periods of easy predation. Indeed, given that sleep essentially knocks animals out, often for hours at a time, it is safe to say that sleep is the single most dangerous activity animals engage in over the course of their lives. And yet animals do it day after day from the moment they're born to the day they die.

They do so because that's the trade-off that must be endured for animals to learn. For only during sleep's enforced state of external unconsciousness can animals' learning networks pause the generation of new memories so they can begin processing the day's existing set of short-term memories. The end result is that during sleep, animals learn by keeping valuable memories while disregarding those with weak valuation tags.

As such, the theory that animals sleep in order to learn provides the most logical explanation for not only why animals sleep but also why it occurs in every animal that is able to learn. Alternate hypotheses for why animals sleep, such as engaging in energy allocation⁵, servicing a body's essential metabolic functions⁶, or enabling an animal to better adapt to the Earth's diurnal cycle⁷, do not adequately explain why falling into a state of external

unconsciousness is a necessary condition for these activities to occur. Simply put, each of these suggested reasons for sleeping could be carried out just as easily while animals are awake and, thus, without having to render themselves uniquely vulnerable to predation.

In contrast, if animals are sleeping to learn, this would explain the need for them to enter into a state of unconsciousness when they sleep. That's because new memory generation must stop for valuable short-term memories to be identified and retained. However, a significant argument against sleep's purpose of enabling animals to learn is that other biological processes beyond neurological ones are thought to occur while animals sleep.⁸ As such, if sleep is intended to enable animals to benefit from processing valuable short-term memories into long-term ones so they can learn from them, then logic would dictate that only processes relating to this fundamental neurological activity should occur during sleep. But we know this is not the case, as bodily-related functions also occur during sleep.⁹

The answer to this quite valid objection is that just as sleep, among other things, enables an animal's learning network to clear its short-term memories so it can take in new memories when it awakes, it seems logical that during sleep, an animal's entire body would be rejuvenating itself for the same purpose. So, the therapeutic effects often seen in animals' bodies while they sleep are likely done to prime animals' sensory input systems, along with other related systems (perhaps down to a cellular level), for when they awake.

The end result is that when animals wake up, both their brains and their bodies are at the highest state of readiness for taking in new memories, which they can then learn from once they go back to sleep.

III. The Dynamic Information Valuation Mechanisms of Pain and Pleasure Are Likely as Ubiquitous Among Animals as Sleep Is.

Supporting the theory that sleep is ubiquitous in neural-based animals because it is the process by which they learn are studies showing that sleep occurs even in animals lacking complex brains, such as jellyfish and hydras.^{10 11} Bolstering this theory are studies showing that animals such as jellyfish are also able to learn.¹² And given the presence of neuron-like structures in sponges, which may be the earliest form of neural-based life, it seems likely that every species possessing neurons or neuron-like structures engages in some form of sleep while also possessing the ability to learn.¹³

With more and more scientific data slowly eroding the belief that sleep only occurs in animals with complex brains¹⁴, this paper proposes that once animals' memory-based sensory and emotion tags are identified, it will be seen that these information valuation mechanisms are just as ubiquitous in the animal kingdom as sleep is. As such, they will be identified not just in animals with complex brains, but in the case of sensory-based pain and pleasure tags, they will be found in all animals, including those with rudimentary brains, and even in those possessing nerve nets and neuron-like structures. This is because these memory tagging mechanisms are a fundamental part of how all animals learn.

As to the nature of the sensations of pain and pleasure and the possibility of their existing even in animals with rudimentary brains or even simpler nerve nets or neuron-like structures, it is proposed that such sensations are cognitive-based and thus are consciously felt, even at a quite primitive level, in all animals that are capable of learning. It is further asserted that these sensations have to exist because no other mechanism is available for such species to assign value to their memories. And without such a valuation mechanism, learning can't take place because learning is fundamentally about making information valuation determinations.

So, regarding how even primitive species such as sponges could be considered conscious, it is proposed that consciousness arises from the ability to perceive multiple frames of reference simultaneously. Which means that even at the level of individual neurons, or at the even more primitive level of neuron-like structures such as those found in sponges, these cellular components could possess a form of consciousness. This would be the case if they had an awareness of the present, such as, for example, in the form of environmental inputs, while simultaneously being aware of the past, such as in the form of neurally stored sensory information. As such, it is proposed that consciousness could arise even in individual neurons or neuron-like structures.

With pain and pleasure enabling a primitive form of awareness in the earliest evolved neural-based species, it is asserted that evolution soon selected for improved methods of information valuation and awareness. These came in the form of emotions, which, as previously noted, likely evolved from the base sensations of pain and pleasure.

As a second information valuation mechanism, emotions are also obviously cognitive-based. But, due to their being more informationally nuanced versions of pain and pleasure, they require more complex neural structures with greater processing power to generate and utilize them. So, they will be found in all mammals and birds. And, likely, they will also be found in most reptiles, fish, and other species with higher-order brains, such as squids and octopuses. Simply put, it is proposed they'll be found in any species that possess amygdalas or amygdala-like cognitive structures, which are responsible for generating the emotion tags that are hypothesized to assign value to memories.

As to the term 'emotion,' it is submitted this is the correct usage to apply to all such memory markers, no matter the species possessing them, because they are mental feelings that allow animals to consciously assess the relative importance of their interactions with their

environment. A potential objection to this assertion is that to ascribe such mental feelings to other animals is to engage in anthropomorphism. However, the concept of anthropomorphism may itself be anthropomorphic, given that it ascribes a uniqueness and, indeed, a superiority to human biological processes that simply does not exist.

5 So, just as humans share DNA with all living animals, it is submitted that humans share the same basic sensations of pain and pleasure, albeit often in less cognitively aware forms, with all other animals, and emotions with a great many as well.¹⁵ Once this is shown, it will demonstrate that humans share essentially the same biological mechanisms for learning that every other learning-based species possesses. And the proof for this assertion will be in the
10 identification of our memories' respective sensory and emotion tags, followed by their tracing back to species with earlier evolved versions.

IV. How the Information Valuation Mechanism of Pain and Pleasure First Evolved

 It is proposed that all life requires some form of information valuation in order to survive.
15 The most basic form of information valuation occurs through the selection of genetic information via reproduction and natural selection. But the problem with this form of information valuation is it essentially remains static until an organism reproduces. To respond to this challenge, species evolved dynamic information valuation mechanisms that enabled information's value to be updated much more quickly, even to the extent of it being valued on a moment to moment
20 basis.

 As such, it is submitted that the first dynamic valuation mechanism came in the form of microorganisms' development of proto-immune-like responses to outside attackers. Specifically, this first dynamic mechanism likely evolved to enable microorganisms to distinguish between

helpful foreign particles like food and harmful ones like pathogens.¹⁶ Thus, proto-immune-like systems formed life's first dynamic learning system, albeit at a cellular level.¹⁷

As for life's first consciousness-based information valuation mechanism, which collectively are the base sensations of pain and pleasure, it is proposed that this mechanism was developed by re-purposing certain capacities of life's earlier evolved learning system, otherwise known as the innate immune system.¹⁸

In this regard, it has been persuasively theorized that neural information processing likely began with a combined sensory-neuro-type structure.¹⁹ This type of structure started as a sensor mechanism that then triggered an action. Then, a proto-neural part was added to the cellular structure. This enabled sensory-generated information to be taken in and transmitted to and stored in the proto-neural part of the structure. Upon such information being recognized and stored, the pre-existing action part of this structure then triggered a response. So these proto-neurons were able to induce actions in an organism without requiring a central nervous system to function.

For example, one form of these proto-neurons could have evolved to detect digestible carbon-based particles, with an action to consume such particles then being triggered. These initial proto-neurons might have been followed by others that could identify non-carbon-based particles, which, upon detection, resulted in the proto-neurons triggering an action to expel such particles.

Thereafter, it is proposed that evolution repurposed several aspects of organisms' innate immune systems to enhance the information-processing power of these proto-neurons. First and most critically, it is submitted that this information processing system required a new information valuation mechanism to function. As such, evolution likely repurposed the closest

available equivalent, which was the innate immune system's valuation mechanism for distinguishing between an organism's own cellular components and foreign invaders.²⁰

So if an action a proto-neuron triggered resulted in the organism's health deteriorating, that information could be transmitted back to the proto-neuron to be stored along with the information that had initially triggered the action. With proto-neurons now receiving information valuations on their actions, which likely evolved quite quickly into sensations of pain and pleasure, they could begin learning similarly to how the innate immune system was already doing.

After that inflection point, evolution could have quickly selected for one-way information transmission pathways to evolve into two-way pathways. So, with immune-like components developing chemical pathways to transmit information to the first neuron-like cells, they could then begin receiving information back thru these same chemical channels. Once that happened, the floodgates would have opened for proto-neurons to start transmitting information to each other.

From there, the next step would have been the evolution of a proto-nervous system. This would have allowed triggering signals from specialized information-processing proto-neurons to be transmitted at a distance to specialized action-triggering proto-neurons. In turn, this would have enabled organisms to begin developing extended multi-cellular body plans.

A relatively simple example of how such a proto-nervous system might have evolved would be for a set of proto-neurons that had detected a nearby heat source to send signals via repurposed immune-like chemical transmitters (such as cytokines) to other neurons that had specialized in triggering an organism to move. So, one set of heat-detecting proto-neurons could have used the proto-immune system's chemical pathways to send signals to another set of proto-neurons to begin moving away from the potentially harmful heat source.

It is submitted that after an information storage mechanism had been developed, along with a mechanism to assign value to such information, certain aspects of the innate immune system were repurposed a third time, leading to the resetting of proto-neurons. So, in the case of proto-neurons with sufficiently weak pain/pleasure valuations, they would have been identified and then reset in order to take in new information. This is how sleep would have first evolved. And, as noted before, its purpose would have been to shut off the intake of new sensory information so that proto-neurons and, later on, actual neurons could be made ready to store new and potentially more valuable information.

With proto-immune system functions being repurposed to aid in the evolution of neurons, nervous systems, and, ultimately, brains, this would explain why various cellular components and chemical transmitters, such as cytokines, complement proteins, and certain types of glial cells, such as phagocytes, astrocytes, oligodendrocytes, radial glia, and Schwann cells, have significant roles in the functioning of both immune systems and neurological systems.²¹

V. Pain and Pleasure as the First Neural-Based Information Valuation Mechanism

As to the base sensations of pain and pleasure, this paper asserts that the entire reason they were evolutionarily selected for is to provide value determinations on information. Specifically, they evolved to provide value determinations as to which sensory-derived information should be immediately acted upon via cognitive-based structures and then retained for learning purposes.

So painful and pleasurable reactions to sensory information serve as indirect markers for the presence of neurons or neuron-like structures in animals and even in the earliest evolved species. Furthermore, as the first valuation mechanism for cognitively stored information, pain and pleasure are, as noted before, consciously dependent sensations rather than physical

sensations. Which explains why reactions to painful interactions, even in the earliest evolved animal species, are tempered when analgesics are applied, or eliminated outright in the case of anesthetics.^{22 23} As such, this paper proposes that pain and pleasure's biological components will be found in all animals with cognitive-based learning networks, from the most primitive to the most complex.

Regarding their scope, pain and pleasure evolved so that no matter what environment an animal encountered, the sensory information derived therefrom could be interpreted via a single metric. Whether the interaction involved environmental conditions (such as in the case of heat, cold, acidity, or salinity) or an environmental encounter resulting in, for example, a successful mating or a nearly fatal attack, all could be measured on a continuum thru the yardstick of pain and pleasure.

And in serving as valuation tags or markers for sensory information that was being cognitively stored, pain and pleasure could themselves begin triggering reactions. So, a pain valuation would indicate to a proto-neuron that the action it had initiated was harmful, thereby resulting in its stopping the action. Or it might trigger a contrary reaction, such as by signaling to an organism to move away from whatever was causing the feeling of pain. In contrast, a pleasure tag would indicate an action was helpful, so the proto-neuron should continue triggering the action. This system would not only enable organisms to immediately respond to environmental cues, but also enable them to learn from sensory-derived information. As such, this is how a new learning system could have evolved without neurons or a nervous system initially being present.

As an example of this, if a relatively simple multi-cellular organism, such as a sponge, just ate, the sense of pleasure derived from that activity would be used to mark the sensory information associated with the event – in other words, the 'what', 'when' and 'where' of the

event. This pleasure-tagged information would then get stored in neuron precursors, such as a sponge's neuroid cells.²⁴ Once multi-cellular organisms were able to recall such information, such as by new sensory data triggering the same proto-neuron into action, even relatively simple animals such as sponges could start learning.

5 Using pain and pleasure to mark memories for assessment could then potentially explain several curiosities seen in animal biology and behavior. The first of these curiosities is biology-based. It involves finding neuron-like structures, that are associated with digestion, in sponges, which lack both neurons and a nervous system.²⁵ It is proposed that such structures may have evolved in order to detect when a sponge has fed, thereby enabling the information associated
10 with that critically important behaviour to be immediately stored. This would, in turn, allow for learning to take place based on the pleasure-marking of the information.

 Relatedly, this might also explain why all animals with a central nervous system possess a 'second brain' in their digestive systems, which is otherwise known as the enteric nervous system.²⁶ This second or, in reality, 'first' brain (given that it evolved before the central nervous
15 system) was likely selected for because it enabled animals' learning networks to exercise a great degree of control over when and what they ate.

 Another curiosity associated with the use of pain and pleasure as a valuation mechanism is behaviour-based. Specifically, it involves the behaviour of feeling sleepy after eating a big meal that many animals, including humans, demonstrate.²⁷ This could be a valuable information
20 processing tactic descended from when primitive animals first began using the base feelings of pleasure and pain to mark memories for retention. So animals get sleepy after enjoying a big meal because their learning networks recognize, based on the pleasure-tagging of the memories associated with this activity, that something highly informationally valuable has just occurred.

As a result, a feeling of sleepiness is triggered. After an animal goes to sleep, its brain is then able to rapidly capture the valuable information that led to the big meal and learn from it.

Similarly, when males of different species have sex, there is anecdotal evidence that they tend to feel tired afterward. This phenomenon has been so widely observed, particularly as it relates to humans, that it is often remarked upon in humorous articles on the topic.²⁸ So, in the case of after-sex, the brain triggers a feeling of sleepiness in males to capture the information associated with the evolutionarily critical activity of reproduction. And brains, and even simpler neural networks, may have been engaging in these sorts of sleep-based information-capturing activities since animals first evolved consciousness-based learning networks.

So, in conclusion, the sensations of pain and pleasure should be thought of as a single information valuation mechanism, which evolution selected for in the earliest cognitive-based species to distinguish between useful and useless information and thereby make neural-based learning possible.

VI. Emotions as a More Nuanced Information Value Mechanism

Emotions evolved from the first cognitive-based valuation mechanism of pain and pleasure in order to provide more nuanced valuations for information stored in neurons. As such, cognitive-based systems used the same memory tagging mechanism for emotions as was being used for pain/pleasure valuations. And as with pain and pleasure, emotion tags allowed brains to determine whether a memory, based on the strength of these tags, was sufficiently valuable that it should be kept during sleep. The same mechanism then allowed memories with relevant emotion tags to be recalled while an animal was awake.

So, just as evolution's information processing imperative utilized the foundation of proto-immune signaling to bootstrap pain and pleasure as a valuation mechanism, pain and pleasure

were then used, in turn, to bootstrap the evolution of a second, more potent mechanism for evaluating information. Emotions should thus be viewed as higher-level flavors or echoes of the base cognitive sensations of pain and pleasure.²⁹ This almost certainly explains why they often produce unpleasant physical sensations in the case of negative emotions and pleasant physical sensations in the case of positive ones. This is so because, as the valuational heirs of pain and pleasure, emotions almost certainly have similar underlying neurobiological compositions, but more on this connection later.^{30 31}

Regarding the need for emotions, they provided valuation assessments for memories to enable learning but in much more effective ways. And indeed, they were likely a critical factor in the development of complex capabilities such as brooding and child-rearing, as will also be discussed later.³² As to how they enabled more complex learning capabilities, they did so first by allowing species to consider their reactions to environmental actions at a much more conscious level than at the nearly automatic level typically triggered by pleasant and, particularly, painful sensations and associations.

Second, with consciousness having evolved in species to give a greater, more multi-faceted sense of the present, utilizing emotions as information valuation tags enabled species to avoid regurgitating memorialized sensations of pain or pleasure. Such sensations likely proved problematic at a conscious level because they might not only overwhelm an animal's ability to generate informationally comprehensive new memories, but they might also sidetrack animals from effectively responding to whatever dangers or potentially rewarding activities they were facing at any particular moment in time.

Finally, and perhaps most importantly, emotions enabled species to respond in more nuanced ways to environmental interactions than the blunt sensations of pain and pleasure were capable of. So memories could be stored with a variety of emotion tags and even combinations

of them, which would then help animals to respond to external events in much more adaptively appropriate ways. This would be in contrast to the more instantaneous 'fight or flight' response a pain-marked memory might trigger or the nearly automatic behavioural response of wanting 'more' in the case of pleasure-marked memories.^{33,34}

5 As an example, a memory marked with a negative emotion might produce a feeling of anger in some cases or fear or revulsion in others. In each case, a completely different yet adaptively appropriate response would be the result. Or, a memory marked with a positive emotion might result in a mental feeling of happiness or satisfaction in some cases or curiosity in another depending on the environmental cues triggering the memory's recall. The actions
10 resulting from these positive emotions would then be completely different based not only on the emotion but on the context of their recall.

 Accordingly, the adaptive power of emotions as the second evolved mechanism for evaluating memories is obvious. Different emotions, though ultimately based on the fundamental sensations of pain and pleasure, enabled animals to react in entirely different ways
15 depending on what was the most adaptively suitable response to the particular circumstances they found themselves in.

VII. The Evolution of the Emotion of Empathy as a Key Cognitive Development

 It seems likely that the evolution of the emotion of empathy, along with its sister
20 emotions of compassion, sympathy, and pity, led to a dramatic change in species' behaviour, as well as in species' cognitive abilities.³⁵ As to why this occurred, it is theorized that empathy, compassion, sympathy, pity, and other related emotions are the first complex emotions to have evolved among animal species.³⁶

What makes such emotions complex is they are essentially double-layered, which means the mental feelings they produce are based on how one thinks another is feeling. So, in effect, these complex emotions produce two levels of emotions. One that is felt by the empathizer and another that is perceived as being felt by the subject of the empathetic feeling.

5 As to the change these emotions promoted in species' behaviour, it appears that this expansion of species' emotional toolkits led to animals beginning to care for their young.³⁷ Which, in turn, became a significant driver of brain expansion, likely due to child-rearing being one of the most complex activities animals engage in.³⁸ This is the case because child-rearing is one of the few animal behaviors that extends out over weeks, months, and sometimes even years
10 while simultaneously requiring animals to provide for themselves and their children, as well as in having to act to protect both themselves and their children.

 With the evolution of complex emotions leading to offspring-protecting and child-rearing behaviours, this necessarily resulted in animals becoming concerned, for the first time, with the survival of others. Those others would have started off with their children, then their mates, and
15 then, subsequently, even their kin. This behavioural change would have been in stark contrast with the behaviour of animals who remained focused solely on their own survival.

 The evolution of emotions concerned with the well-being of others thus propelled animals into the second great leap in consciousness. The initial leap occurred when animals' neural structures made them aware of their environments. The second leap then occurred when
20 empathetic emotions opened animals' eyes to the difference between themselves and others. The end result was that the evolution of complex emotions led to animals becoming self-aware.

VIII. The Evolution of Complex Emotions Led to Problem-Solving Behaviours

It is asserted that when the lineage of our emotions is tracked backward in evolutionary history, it will be found that the 'motherly' emotions such as empathy, affection, love, protectiveness, tenderness, and worry developed in the first child-protecting species.

5 Specifically, it is proposed that the evolution of such 'motherly' emotions likely occurred around the time species began protecting their eggs after they were laid. From there, yet further emotions evolved relating to the guarding and nurturing of children, leading to species beginning to protect and teach their children after they hatched or were born. So, it is hypothesized that the development of the first 'motherly' emotions is actually what led to these child-protecting
10 behaviours. And at each stage, species' brains expanded to help animals successfully act upon these emotions that were, in effect, encouraging their nurturing behaviors.³⁹

With the expansion of brains being propelled by the complex behaviours required to successfully protect and then rear animals' offspring, it is asserted that this led to the third leap in consciousness observed in animals, which is problem-solving behaviour. More precisely, what
15 the third leap in consciousness allowed animals to do is create new ideas. And in doing so, what was actually happening in animals' minds is that they were projecting themselves into the future to anticipate the results of their new ideas.

This is how the imagination first evolved. So, once an animal developed a new idea that led to a successful problem-solving behaviour, the behaviour could then be taught to others. As
20 such, in species possessing 'motherly' emotions, we'll likely find that many of them possess the ability to problem-solve.

Specifically, we'll find complex 'motherly' emotions in all mammals and birds, likely in crocodiles and even in some species of snakes such as cobras and pythons and other reptiles such as monitor lizards. And, finally, we'll possibly even find them in some species of fish. Once

we're able to identify the genes associated with the development of such emotions, we may even find them in some species of dinosaurs that cared for their young, assuming, of course, that we're ultimately able to find the DNA for a wide variety of dinosaur species.

Thus, it is proposed that empathetic emotions came first in one or more species, which led to the guarding and nurturing of the eggs they laid. This, in turn, led to bigger brains, which evolved to carry out the more complex activities associated with caring for one's young.⁴⁰ And as child protection and rearing become even more involved, and with such activities taking place over progressively longer periods, this led to the progression in brain size that we see in many species, along with a cognitive leap in consciousness as evidenced by problem-solving behaviours.⁴¹

And with brain size generally increasing in proportion to how much time and effort a species puts into caring for their young,⁴² we will likely find in the future that some species with comparatively large brain sizes, such as, for example, certain species of sharks, that are generally presumed not to care for their young, actually do care for them in some fashion. And in such species, problem-solving behaviours will also likely be evident.

IX. Dreaming Is Likely Nearly as Widespread Among Animals as Emotions Are

It is submitted that dreaming exists to improve learning. As such, dreaming occurs after new memories are woven into animals' long-term memory frameworks during sleep. What dreaming does (which this paper suggests should be relabeled the 'dreaming' stage of sleep rather than the rapid-eye movement ("REM") stage of sleep) is ensure new memories are not only properly stored but that their informational relevance is properly measured and assessed for recall when an animal awakes.

This is why dreaming emulates wakefulness, with brain waves generally being unsynchronized, except as to the gamma wave oscillations seen during both dreaming and wakefulness,⁴³ as well why dreams typically have life-like narrative structures. Dreaming thus serves to trigger the recall of newly stored memories, just as might occur during wakefulness, but with the brain having much greater control over their manner of recall.

This process, it is submitted, is what enables the refinement of learning, thus explaining why disruptions to the dreaming stage of sleep can have a significant impact on the recall of physical as well as mental skills that have been newly learned.⁴⁴ And with nearby, yet potentially unrelated, thoughts, ideas, and associations being activated during this process, this further explains why dreams can seem so real while at the same time being so disjointed.

The critical nature of both storing adaptively valuable information and ensuring its wakeful relevance thus points to the strong likelihood that many animals dream while they're asleep.⁴⁵ Accordingly, it is proposed that dreaming occurs in many vertebrate species with REM or REM-like phases of sleep, which again this paper proposes should be relabeled as the 'dreaming' stage of sleep. So, this will likely hold true for all mammals, birds, and most, if not all, reptiles, and possibly fish. It is also possible, and perhaps even likely, that dreaming may be occurring in invertebrate species like cephalopods.

X. The Neurological Basis for Learning Thru Information Valuation

If pain and pleasure and emotions act as information valuation mechanisms to enable learning, how do they do so at a neurological level? It is proposed they do so by being stored as markers or tags in memories. Specifically, they are hypothesized to be written into the presynaptic membranes of neurons when synaptic vesicles operate in kiss-and-run mode,⁴⁶ with

slow oscillation brain waves⁴⁷ in the range of 0.5 to 1.0 Hz likely being the signature of action potentials triggering this activity.

The manner in which they are asserted to be written into the presynaptic membrane is by vesicles docking at active zones⁴⁸ on the presynaptic membrane. Lipid rafts⁴⁹ then act as transport mediums for transferring information to and from scaffolding protein complexes.⁵⁰ located in the presynaptic membrane. As such, scaffolding protein complexes are hypothesized to be the ultimate site of memory storage, including that of the sensory and emotion tags that are asserted to be critical to the retention of memories.

But even if this hypothesis ultimately turns out to be incorrect, what is not subject to dispute is neurotransmitters are involved in the formation and signaling of both pain and pleasure and emotions.^{51 52} Even more pertinently, there is a significant overlap in neurotransmitters involved in feelings of pleasure and positive emotions (such as dopamine, oxytocin, serotonin, endorphins, and norepinephrine),⁵³ as well as in feelings of pain and negative emotions (e.g., glutamate and gamma-aminobutyric acid).⁵⁴ It is submitted that this correlation is not accidental and should be viewed as significant evidence of an evolutionary association, with pain and pleasure's neurological components having evolved into emotions once brains developed emotion-generating structures like the amygdala.

Lastly, the fact that neurotransmitters associated with pleasure and pain are found even in ancient species such as sponges provides significant evidence for the hypothesis that animal species possessing only neuron-like structures are nevertheless capable of feeling pain and pleasure at a basic level.⁵⁵ So if ancient animal species such as sponges can feel pain and pleasure, the logical conclusion to draw from this is that pain and pleasure evolved as the first neural-based information valuation mechanism, which then led to the evolution of emotions.

XI. Sleep's Enabling of Learning

It is submitted that sleep's function is to enable learning. As discussed in prior sections, sleep does this at a basic level by shutting down the generation of new memories so that valuable short-term memories can be identified and transferred to long-term storage. Once an animal wakes, relevant memories not only serve to guide behaviour but become the building blocks for skills that enable survival.

The stages of sleep demonstrate how this occurs. In the first stage of what is known as non-rapid eye movement ("NREM") sleep, this is marked by a light transitional state that typically lasts just a few minutes.⁵⁶ It is submitted that there are two purposes for this transitional state. The first is to allow the brain sufficient time to shut down sensory inputs that would otherwise result in the generation of new memories. The second is to prime certain parts of the brain for the next stage of NREM sleep, otherwise known as stage 2 of sleep. As to how this occurs, the thalamus is hypothesized to be primarily responsible for the process of shutting down sensory functions (such as seeing, hearing, and feeling). This is likely the case given that it appears to be the central hub both thru which memories are generated and consciousness arises.⁵⁷

In stage 2 of NREM sleep,⁵⁸ it is submitted that cognitive structures in the brain, particularly associated with the thalamus, begin marking valuable short-term memories for transfer to long-term storage. Sleep spindles⁵⁹, in the frequency range of 11 to 16 Hz, along with K-complexes,⁶⁰ which contain dominant frequency components in the range of 0.5-4.0 Hz, are proposed to be the brain wave signatures associated with this activity. Specifically, it is asserted they are the aggregate signatures of action potentials triggering vesicles to mark valuable information for transfer that is stored in the presynaptic membranes of short-term memory neurons.

As this occurs, delta waves, in the frequency range of 1 to 4 Hz, are also seen during stage 2 of sleep, though not nearly at the level seen during stage 3 of NREM sleep.^{61 62} It is proposed that these delta waves are the signature of action potentials triggering vesicles to operate in kiss-and-run mode. The purpose of this is to erase short-term memories with little to no value, principally as determined by the relative weakness of their sensory and/or emotion tags.

The presence of differing types of brain waves during particular stages of sleep thus raises the possibility that the stages of sleep are not as sequential as they might otherwise seem.⁶³ So it is hypothesized that the functions of each stage actually overlap on a consistent basis.⁶⁴ As such, while delta waves are normally seen during stage 3 of sleep, the fact that they can also occur during stage 2 of sleep should be viewed as evidence that the erasure of short-term memories is being carried out in both stages of sleep. So, memories having little to no informational value get discarded, likely during stage 2 of sleep. While highly valuable memories that have already been transferred to long-term memory get erased in stage 3. The end result is short-term memory is cleared to take in new memories when a subject next wakes up.

During stage 3 of sleep, it is proposed that valuable short-term memories, as denoted by the marking they've undergone in stage 2 of sleep, are transferred to long-term memory. High-frequency oscillations in the range of 80 to 250 Hz, and otherwise known as 'ripples', are proposed to be the signature of this activity taking place.⁶⁵ Specifically, what fast ripples signify are valuable short-term memories being read via vesicles operating in collapse mode and then being transmitted thru hippocampal-thalamic fibers to the thalamus.⁶⁶ Then, from the thalamus, they're transferred to the neocortex via thalamocortical fibers.⁶⁷

Once these short-term memories reach the neocortex, they are written into long-term storage. The signature of this activity taking place is proposed to be slow-oscillation waves

occurring in the 0.5 to 1 Hz range.⁶⁸ Specifically, and as noted before, slow oscillations are the signature of action potentials triggering vesicles to write information via their kiss-and-run mode of operation to the presynaptic membranes of neurons in the neocortex.

As with stage 2 of NREM sleep, it is proposed that different functions also occur during stage 3 of sleep. In this case, dreams sometimes occur during stage 3 even though they are typically associated with the last stage of sleep.⁶⁹ As such, because dreaming overlaps between stage 3 of sleep, where little to no eye movement occurs, and the last stage of sleep that is typically defined by rapid eye movement, it is submitted that this stage of sleep is more properly viewed as the ‘dreaming’ stage of sleep.

Regarding the ‘dreaming’ stage of sleep, it is hypothesized that it has multiple functions. The first is akin to a quality control measure and is intended to ensure that short-term memories transferred to the neocortex have been properly written into long-term memory. So activating these memories in order to trigger their recall to the thalamus, as they would be during wakefulness, likely ensures they have been stored properly.⁷⁰

The second reason for the ‘dreaming’ stage of sleep is to enable the rehearsal of memories associated with newly learned physical and mental skills. So, replaying them during dreaming ensures that the sequencing and interconnection of the synapses storing such memories are both confirmed and reinforced. And this likely occurs not just in the neocortex but also in the nervous system. Specifically, it is proposed this occurs with respect to interneurons⁷¹ and motor neurons⁷² that actually execute the commands that result in such skills being carried out.

The third reason for activating transferred memories is to ensure that the postsynaptic membranes associated with newly stored memories are able to properly assess their informational value for recall purposes. This is critical because if such memories are to be made useful, it is not enough that they get stored. Their informational significance and relevance also

have to be measured. It is proposed this happens via postsynaptic membranes lowering or raising their gateways to allow information thru based on the value of the information stored in presynaptic membranes.

5 So, ultimately, what dreaming represents is the purposeful creation of a virtual mental environment that enables newly stored memories to be recalled in much the same way they might be during wakefulness. This process allows the informational context and value of new memories to be accurately ‘gated’ in postsynaptic membranes, thus resulting in the direct refinement of learning. This is done during sleep, as opposed to during wakefulness, because the dreaming stage of sleep gives the brain much more control over how newly stored memories are
10 activated and recalled. Furthermore, it is asserted that this is likely the most important part of sleep in relation to long-term potentiation (“LTP”) and long-term depression (“LTD”).⁷³

It is submitted that sleep disruptions support this hypothesis. Specifically, sleep studies indicate that declarative memories benefit from stage 3 of NREM sleep. This correlation makes a great deal of sense if stage 3 is when short-term memories are being transferred to and written
15 into the presynaptic membranes of neurons associated with long-term memory in the neocortex.

With respect to procedural memories, sleep studies indicate that their effective recall benefits significantly from the ‘dreaming’ stage of sleep. This also makes sense if this is the stage of sleep where procedural memories get rehearsed as well as when their informational relevance is measured via gateways in the postsynaptic membrane.⁷⁴

20 And this would also explain why there is a rebound effect after patients stop using anti-depressants.⁷⁵ That’s because one of the side effects of anti-depressant usage is that dreaming stops.⁷⁶ So, with procedural memories being transferred to and stored in the neocortex during stage 3 of sleep, the necessary follow-on step of information assessment and gating doesn’t take

place. Instead, this follow-on step has to wait until anti-depressant usage ends and dreaming starts up again.⁷⁷

Additional support for the dreaming hypotheses presented in this paper can be seen in the curious lack of REM sleep seen in cetaceans.⁷⁸ This has long been considered a mystery in sleep research because many other mammalian species do experience rapid eye movement during sleep. It is proposed that the reason for the discrepancy between cetaceans and other mammals is that cetaceans' primary sense isn't seeing but hearing.

So, if dreaming's purpose is to refine valuable memories in order to enable learning, it seems likely that cetaceans' most important memories will be aural in nature.⁷⁹ Whereas with humans and other land-based mammalian species, their most important memories will be visual in nature. As a result, humans and other eye-dominant species experience REM sleep because they are seeing their memories during sleep. While whales and dolphins are hearing their memories during sleep.

Lastly, regarding the deleterious impact interruptions of stage 3 sleep have on bodily functions and overall health, it is asserted there is a straightforward explanation for this. Both the brain and the nervous system have mechanisms in place to clear the waste products resulting from action potentials firing in neurons throughout the brain and the body.⁸⁰ So if stage 3 of sleep is interrupted, these clearing mechanisms cannot do their jobs. This is why disrupting stage 3 sleep not only has a negative impact on brain functioning but on the health of the body as well.

To this end, it seems quite curious that a notable symptom of diseases such as Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, and Huntington's are delta waves occurring during wakefulness that are normally only seen during sleep.^{81 82 83} With there typically being a build-up of pathological protein aggregates in all three of these diseases,^{84 85 86} could it be that there is a unified

explanation for their presence along with the negative health consequences that result from stage 3 sleep disruption?

So, if action potentials firing in a coordinated manner during sleep result in an accumulation of harmful byproducts, might not the inability of stage 3's clearing mechanisms to operate during sleep disruption, as well as during wakefulness in the case of Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, and Huntington's, explain at least some of the health consequences resulting from both types of dysfunction?

XII. Implications for Neuroscience, Evolution and AI

If the theories presented in this paper are correct, it reframes how the brain is operating. So, if pain and pleasure and emotions evolved as information valuation mechanisms, the value they assign to memories has to be stored in memories. This means neurons at a fundamental level must be storing information in order to process it.

As such, this paper proposes that information, and, in particular, sensory and emotion tags that assign value to memories, are stored in neurons' presynaptic membranes. But wherever such information is actually located, it must have value assigned to it for learning to occur. Once value is assigned to memories, the brain must then have some way of keeping valuable memories while disregarding the rest. It is proposed that sleep is the mechanism that does this.

And with sleep increasingly being viewed as ubiquitous among neural-based species, so to will pain and pleasure eventually be viewed as a nearly universal mechanism for valuing information once their sensory tags are identified. If the emotion tags this paper asserts exist are subsequently identified and found to have evolved from pain and pleasure, then that should go far towards demonstrating that both pain and pleasure and emotions serve fundamentally as information valuation mechanisms. Not only that, but in assigning value to information, it will

be demonstrated that they are the key mechanisms that enable learning to take place.

Furthermore, once emotions' evolutionary lineages are traced back, their genetic history will likely show that humans share them to varying extents with all species possessing amygdalas or similar brain structures, thus calling into question the long-held belief that humanity's emotional development is unique.

Finally, if it is demonstrated that pain and pleasure and emotions serve as information valuation mechanisms, this should point the way towards developing artificial intelligence ("AI") systems that are independently intelligent. With humans having invented sophisticated storage structures that have enabled AI's development, it is thus proposed that AI systems will one day be able to learn on their own, with independent intelligence being the result. But that eventuality will require their being provided with mechanisms similar to those that animals possess that will allow them both to independently value information and then selectively retain and recall it.

Footnotes

1. Benjamin G. Farrar, Ljerka Ostojić, Nicola S. Clayton, *The hidden side of animal cognition research: Scientists' attitudes toward bias, replicability and scientific practice* (PLOS ONE, 2021)
5 <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0256607>
2. Michael W. Begun, *Einstein's Masterpiece: Retracing the path to relativity* (The New Atlantis, Fall 2015).
10 <https://www.thenewatlantis.com/publications/einsteins-masterpiece>
3. Chiara Cirelli, Giulio Tonoi, *Is Sleep Essential* (PLOS Biology, 2008).
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2525690/>
4. Id.
5. Markus H. Schmidt, Kaspar A. Schindler, *Cellular Stress, Energy Constraints and the Energy Allocation Hypothesis of Sleep* (Clinical and Translational Neuroscience, 2024)
15 <https://www.mdpi.com/2514-183X/8/1/6>
6. Sunil Sharma, Mani Kavuru, *Sleep and Metabolism: An Overview* (International Journal of Endocrinology, 2010)
20 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2929498/>
7. Andrew S. Freiberg, MD, *Why We Sleep: A Hypothesis for an Ultimate or Evolutionary Origin for Sleep and Other Physiological Rhythms* (Journal of Circadian Rhythms, 2020)
25 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7120898/>
8. Fabia M. Stich, Stephanie Huwiler, gommeaar D'Hulst, Caroline Lustenberger, *The Potential Role of Sleep in Promoting a Healthy Body Composition: Underlying Mechanisms Determining Muscle, Fat, and Bone Mass and Their Association with Sleep* (Karger, 2021)
30 <https://karger.com/nen/article/112/7/673/825396/The-Potential-Role-of-Sleep-in-Promoting-a-Healthy>
9. M Dattilo, H K M Antunes, A Mederios, M Mônico Neto, H S Souza, S Tufik, M T de Mello, *Sleep and muscle recovery: endocrinological and molecular basis for a new and promising hypothesis* (Medical Hypotheses, 2011)
35 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21550729/>
10. Alex C. Keene, Erik R. Duboue, *The origins and evolution of sleep* (Journal of Experimental Biology, 2018)
40 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6515771/>
11. Hiroyuki J. Kanaya, Sungeon Park, Ji-hyung Kim, Junko Kusumi, Sofian Krenenou, Etsuko Sawatari, Aya Sato, Jongbin Lee, Hyunwoo Bang, Yoshitaka Kobayakawa, Chunghun Lim, and Taichi Q. Itoh, *A sleep-like state in Hydra unravels conserved sleep mechanisms during the evolutionary development of the central nervous system* (Science Advances, 2020)
45 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7541080>

Footnotes – Continued

- 5 12. Jan Bielecki, Sofie Katrine Dam Nielsen, Gösta Nachman, Anders Garm, *Associative learning in the box jellyfish *Tripedalia cystophora** (Current Biology, 2023)
[https://www.cell.com/current-biology/abstract/S0960-9822\(23\)01136-3](https://www.cell.com/current-biology/abstract/S0960-9822(23)01136-3)
- 10 13. Jacob M. Musser, Klaske J. Schippers, Michael Nickel, Giulia Mizzon, Andrea B. Kohn, Constantin Pape, Jörg U. Hammel, Florian Wolf, Cong Liang, Ana Hernández-Plaza, Kaia Achim, Nicole L. Schieber, Warren R. Francis, View ORCID Profile Sergio Vargas R., Svenja Kling, Maike Renkert, Roberto Feuda, Imre Gaspar, View ORCID Profile Pawel Burkhardt, Peer Bork, Martin Beck, Anna Kreshuk, View ORCID Profile Gert Wörheide, Jaime Huerta-Cepas, Yannick Schwab, Leonid L. Moroz, Detlev Arendt (Science 2019)
Profiling cellular diversity in sponges informs animal cell type and nervous system evolution
<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/758276v1>
- 15 14 Ravi D Nath, Claire N Bedbrook, Michael J Abrams, Ty Basinger, Justin S Bois, David A Prober, Paul W Sternberg, Viviana Gradinaru, Lea Goentoro, *The jellyfish *Cassiopea* exhibits a sleep-like state* (Current Biology 2018)
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5653286/>
- 20 15. *What does it mean to be human* (Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History)
<https://humanorigins.si.edu/evidence/genetics>
- 25 16. Charles A Janeway, Jr, Paul Travers, Mark Walport, Mark J Shlomchik, *Immunobiology: The Immune System in Health and Disease. 5th edition.* (Garland Science 2001)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK2713/>
- 30 17. Mihai G. Netea m.netea@aig.umcn.nl · Jessica Quintin · Jos W.M. van der Meer, *Trained Immunity: A Memory for Innate Host Defense* (Cell Host & Microbe 2011)
[https://www.cell.com/cell-host-microbe/fulltext/S1931-3128\(11\)00128-4](https://www.cell.com/cell-host-microbe/fulltext/S1931-3128(11)00128-4)
- 35 18. Yuri Chaves Martins, Flávia Lima Ribeiro-Gomes, Cláudio Tadeu Daniel-Ribeiro, *A short history of innate immunity* (Memórias do Instituto Oswaldo Cruz 2023)
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10168657/>
- 40 19. G.O. Mackie, *Neuroid conduction and the evolution of conducting tissues* (Q. Rev. Biol. 1970)
<https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/abs/10.1086/406645>
- 45 20. Juan-Manuel Anaya, Ricard Cervera, Adriana Rojas-Villarraga, Yehuda Shoenfeld, Roger A. Levy, *Autoimmunity: From Bench to Bedside* (El Rosario University Press 2013)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK459455/>
21. Robert Danzer, *Neuroimmune Interactions: From the Brain to the Immune System and Vice Versa* (Physiological Reviews 2018)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5866360/>

Footnotes – Continued

22. P.G. Morgan, E.B. Kayser, M.M. Sedensky, *C. elegans and volatile anesthetics* (WormBook 2007)
5 http://www.wormbook.org/chapters/www_anesthetics/anesthetics.html
23. Maldonado, H., Miralto, A. *Effect of morphine and naloxone on a defensive response of the mantis shrimp* (Journal of Comparative Physiology 1982)
10 <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/BF00612010>
24. Michael Marshall, *Brainless sponges have cells that might be the precursors of neurons* (New Scientist, 2021)
15 <https://www.newscientist.com/article/2296329-brainless-sponges-have-cells-that-might-be-the-precursors-of-neurons/>
25. Jacob M. Musser, Klaske J. Schippers, Michael Nickel, Giulia Mizzon, Andrea B. Kohn, Constantin Pape, Paolo Ronchi, Nikolaos Papadopoulos, Alexander J. Tarashansky, Detlev Arendt, *Profiling cellular diversity in sponges informs animal cell type and nervous system evolution* (Science 2021)
20 <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.abj2949>
26. J.B. Furness, M.J. Stebbing, *The first brain: Species comparisons and evolutionary implications for the enteric and central nervous systems* (Neurogastroenterology & Motility 2017)
25 <https://rest.neptune-prod.its.unimelb.edu.au/server/api/core/bitstreams/27832a48-9421-5e26-b277-803f6e64896d/content>
27. Thomas Gallagher, Young-Jai You, *Falling asleep after a big meal* (Worm 2014)
30 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4091210/>
28. Melinda Wenner Moy, *Why do guys get sleepy after sex?* (LiveScience 2022)
35 <https://www.livescience.com/32445-why-do-guys-get-sleepy-after-sex.html>
29. Morten L. Kringelbach, Kent C. Berridge, *The Affective Core of Emotion: Linking Pleasure, Subjective Well-Being, and Optimal Metastability in the Brain* (Emotion Review, 2018)
40 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5604465/>
30. Shazia R. Chaudhry, William Gossman, *Biochemistry, Endorphin* (StatPearls Publishing 2025)
45 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470306/>
31. Meihong Li, Kepeng She, Pengfei Zhu, Zhen Li, Jieqiong Liu, Fang Luo, Yingze Ye, *Chronic Pain and Comorbid Emotional Disorders: Neural Circuitry and Neuroimmunity Pathways* (International Journal of Molecular Sciences 2025)
50 <https://www.mdpi.com/1422-0067/26/2/436>

Footnotes – Continued

32. Frans B.M. de Waal, *Putting the Altruism Back into Altruism: The Evolution of Empathy* (Annual Review of Psychology 2008)
5 https://www.emory.edu/LIVING_LINKS/publications/articles/deWaal_2008.pdf
33. Jaime Vila, Pedro Guerra, Miguel Ángel Muñoz, Cynthia Vico, Maria Isabel Viedma-del Jesús, Luís Carlos Delgado, Pandelis Perakakis, Elisabeth Kley, José Luís Mata, Sonia Rodríguez, *Cardiac defense: From attention to action* (International Journal of Psychophysiology 2007)
10 https://pandelisperakakis.info/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/Cardiac-defense-From-attention-to-action_2007_International-Journal-of-Psychophysiology.pdf
34. James E. Glazera, Nicholas J. Kelleya, Narun Pornpattananangkulb, Vijay A. Mittala, Robin Nusslock, *Beyond the FRN: Broadening the time-course of EEG and ERP components implicated in reward processing* (International Journal of Psychophysiology 2018)
15 https://static1.squarespace.com/static/57ab59ce893fc0d6eb450ccb/t/62e0485fa7f3143f00390734/1658865761246/Glazer_2018_Beyond_FRN_broadening.pdf
- 20 35. Jules H. Masserman, M.D., Stanley Wechkin, PH.D., William Terris, “*Altruistic*” *Behavior in Rhesus Monkeys* (American Journal of Psychiatry, 1964)
<http://www.primateliberty.com/masserman.pdf>
36. Jaak Panksepp, Jules B. Panksepp, *Toward a cross-species understanding of empathy* (Trends in Neurosciences 2013)
25 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3839944/>
37. de Waal, *Putting the Altruism Back into Altruism: The Evolution of Empathy*
30 https://www.emory.edu/LIVING_LINKS/publications/articles/deWaal_2008.pdf
38. Carel P. van Schaik, Zitan Song, Caroline Schuppli, Szymon M. Drobniak, Sandra A. Heldstab, Michael Griesser, *Extended parental provisioning and variation in vertebrate brain sizes* (PLOS Biology 2023)
35 <https://journals.plos.org/plosbiology/article?id=10.1371/journal.pbio.3002016>
39. J. L. Edgar, J. C. Lowe, E. S. Paul, C. J. Nicol, *Avian maternal response to chick distress* (Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences 2011)
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3158930/>
- 40 40. van Schaik, Song, Schuppli, Drobniak, Heldstab, Griesser, *Extended parental provisioning and variation in vertebrate*
<https://journals.plos.org/plosbiology/article?id=10.1371/journal.pbio.3002016>
41. Natalie Uomini, Joanna Fairlie, Russell D Gray, Michael Griesser, *Extended parenting and the evolution of cognition* (Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences 2020)
45 <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7293161/>

Footnotes – Continued

- 5 42. Robert A Barton, Isabella Capellini, *Maternal investment, life histories, and the costs of brain growth in mammals* (Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America 2011)
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3076843/>
- 10 43. J. Allan Hobson and Edward F. Pace-Schott, *The cognitive neuroscience of sleep: neuronal systems, consciousness and learning* (Nature Reviews Neuroscience 2002)
http://fisio2.icb.usp.br:4882/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/Sleep_Learning_Nature_Review.pdf
- 15 44. Björn Rasch, Jan Born, *About Sleep's Role in Memory* (Physiological Reviews 2013)
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3768102/>
- 20 45. Kenway Louie, Matthew A. Wilson, *Temporally Structured Replay of Awake Hippocampal Ensemble Activity during Rapid Eye Movement Sleep* (Neuron 2001)
[https://www.cell.com/neuron/fulltext/S0896-6273\(01\)00186-6](https://www.cell.com/neuron/fulltext/S0896-6273(01)00186-6)
- 25 46. Nobutoshi C Harata 1, Alexander M Aravanis, Richard W Tsien, *Kiss-and-run and full-collapse fusion as modes of exo-endocytosis in neurosecretion* (Journal of Neurochemistry 2006)
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1111/j.1471-4159.2006.03987.x>
- 30 47. Richárd Csercsa, Balázs Dombovári, Dániel Fabó, Lucia Wittner, Loránd Eröss, László Entz, András Sólyom, György Rásonyi, Anna Szűcs, Anna Kelemen, Rita Jakus, Vera Juhos, László Grand, Andor Magony, Péter Halász, Tamás F. Freund, Zsófia Maglóczky, Sydney S. Cash, László Papp, György Karmos, Eric Halgren, István Ulbert, *Laminar analysis of slow wave activity in humans* (Brain 2010)
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3105490/>
- 35 48. Thomas C. Südhof, *The Presynaptic Active Zone* (Neuron 2012)
[https://www.cell.com/neuron/fulltext/S0896-6273\(12\)00572-7](https://www.cell.com/neuron/fulltext/S0896-6273(12)00572-7)
- 40 49. Heike Hering, Chih-Chun Lin, Morgan Sheng, *Lipid Rafts in the Maintenance of Synapses, Dendritic Spines, and Surface AMPA Receptor Stability* (Journal of Neuroscience 2003)
- 45 50. Frauke Ackermann, Clarissa L Waites, and Craig C Garner, *Presynaptic active zones in invertebrates and vertebrates* (EMBO reports 2015)
<https://www.embopress.org/doi/full/10.15252/embr.201540434>
51. Chaudhry, Gossman, *Biochemistry, Endorphin*
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470306/>

Footnotes – Continued

52. Li, She, Zhu, Li, Liu, Luo, Ye, *Chronic Pain and Comorbid Emotional Disorders: Neural Circuitry and Neuroimmunity Pathways*
5 <https://www.mdpi.com/1422-0067/26/2/436>
53. Tobias Esch, George B. Stefano, *The neurobiology of pleasure, reward processes, addiction and their health implications* (Neuroendocrinology Letters 2004)
10 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/8352419_The_neurobiology_of_pleasure_reward_processes_addiction_and_their_health_implications
54. Igor Elman, David Borsook, *Threat Response System: Parallel Brain Processes in Pain vis-à-vis Fear and Anxiety* (Frontiers in Psychiatry 2018)
15 <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychiatry/articles/10.3389/fpsy.2018.00029/full>
55. Kornelia Ellwanger, Andre Eich, Michael Nickel, *GABA and glutamate specifically induce contractions in the sponge *Tethya wilhelma** (Journal of Comparative Physiology A: Neuroethology, Sensory, Neural, and Behavioral Physiology 2007)
20 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17021832/>
56. Aakash K. Patel, Vamsi Reddy, Karlie R. Shumway, John F. Araujo, *Physiology, Sleep Stages* (StatPearls Publishing 2025)
25 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK526132/>
57. Lawrence M. Ward, *The thalamic dynamic core theory of conscious experience* (Consciousness and Cognition 2011)
30 <https://cogsys.sites.olt.ubc.ca/files/2016/09/Ward-2011-tdc-new.pdf>
58. Patel, Reddy, Shumway, Araujo, *Physiology, Sleep Stages*
35 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK526132/>
59. Sara C. Mednick, Elizabeth A. McDevitt, James K. Walsh, Erin Wamsley, Martin Paulus, Jennifer C. Kanady, Sean P. A. Drummond, *The Critical Role of Sleep Spindles in Hippocampal-Dependent Memory: A Pharmacology Study* (The Journal of Neuroscience 2013)
40 <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3744388/>
60. Svenja Happe, Peter Anderer, Georg Gruber, Gerhard Klösch, Bernd Saletu, Josef Zeitlhofer, *Scalp Topography of the Spontaneous K-Complex and of Delta-Waves in Human Sleep* (Brain Topography 2002)
45 <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1023/A:1019992523246>
61. Patel, Reddy, Shumway, Araujo, *Physiology, Sleep Stages*
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK526132/>

Footnotes – Continued

- 5 62. Michael J. Prerau, Ritchie E. Brown, Matt T. Bianchi, Jeffrey M. Ellenbogen, Patrick L. Purdon, *Sleep Neurophysiological Dynamics Through the Lens of Multitaper Spectral Analysis* (Physiology 2015)
<https://journals.physiology.org/doi/full/10.1152/physiol.00062.2015>
- 10 63. Francesca Siclari, Giulio Bernardi, Jacinthe Cataldi, Giulio Tononi, *Dreaming in NREM Sleep: A High-Density EEG Study of Slow Waves and Spindles* (Journal of Neuroscience 2018)
<https://www.jneurosci.org/content/jneuro/38/43/9175.full.pdf>
- 15 64. Id.
- 20 65. Birgit Frauscher, Nicolás von Ellenrieder, Rina Zelman, Christine Rogers, Dang Khoa Nguyen, Philippe Kahane, François Dubeau, Jean Gotman, *High-Frequency Oscillations in the Normal Human Brain* (Annals of Neurology 2018)
https://www.mcgill.ca/frauscher-lab/files/frauscher-lab/frauscher_et_al-2018-annals_of_neurology.pdf
- 25 66. John P. Aggleton, Shane M. O'Mara, Seralynne D. Vann, Nick F. Wright, Marian Tsanov, Jonathan T. Erichsen, *Hippocampal–anterior thalamic pathways for memory: uncovering a network of direct and indirect actions* (European Journal of Neuroscience 2010)
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/j.1460-9568.2010.07251.x>
- 30 67. Kevin George, Joe M. Das, *Neuroanatomy, Thalamocortical Radiations* (StatPearls Publishing 2025)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK546699/>
- 35 68. Csercsa, Dombóvári, Fabó, Wittner, Eröss, Entz, Sólyom, Rásonyi, Szücs, Kelemen, Jakus, Juhos, Grand, Magony, Halász, Freund, Maglóczy, Cash, Papp, Karmos, Halgren, Ulbert, *Laminar analysis of slow wave activity in humans*
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3105490/>
- 40 69. Siclari, Bernardi, Cataldi, Tononi, *Dreaming in NREM Sleep: A High-Density EEG Study of Slow Waves and Spindles*
<https://www.jneurosci.org/content/jneuro/38/43/9175.full.pdf>
- 45 70. Mathieu Wolff, Seralynne D. Vann, *The Cognitive Thalamus as a Gateway to Mental Representations* (Journal of Neuroscience 2019)
<https://www.jneurosci.org/content/39/1/3>
71. Adam Kepecs, Gordon Fishell, *Interneuron Cell Types: Fit to form and formed to fit* (Nature 2015)
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC4349583/>

Footnotes – Continued

72. Lindsay C. Zayia, Prasanna Tadi, *Neuroanatomy, Motor Neuron* (StatPearls Publishing 2025)
5 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK554616/>
73. Timothy V.P. Bliss, I Sam F. Cooke, *Long-term potentiation and long-term depression: a clinical perspective* (Clinics 2011)
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/reader/3f55637a5a4c2d949d80d95f8acb1dc061f7780c>
- 10 74. Michael J. Caire, Vamsi Reddy, Matthew A. Varacallo, *Physiology, Synapse* (StatPearls Publishing 2025)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK526047/>
- 15 75. Joshua Feriante Shantanu Singh, *REM Rebound Effect* (StatPearls Publishing 2025)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK560713/>
76. Id.
77. Id.
- 20 78. Oleg I Lyamin, Paul R Manger, Sam H Ridgway, Lev M Mukhametov, Jerome M Siegel, *Cetacean sleep: An unusual form of mammalian sleep* (Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews 2022)
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8742503/>
- 25 79. T. Aran Mooney, Maya Yamato, Brian K. Branstetter, *Hearing in Cetaceans: From Natural History to Experimental Biology* (Advances in Marine Biology 2012)
https://www2.who.edu/site/amooney/wp-content/uploads/sites/31/2018/01/Mooney_et_al_2012_AMB_Hearing_Review_134164.pdf
- 30 80. Lulu Xie¹, Hongyi Kang, Qiwu Xu, Michael J. Chen, Yonghong Liao, Meenakshisundaram Thiagarajan, John O'Donnell, Daniel J. Christensen, Charles Nicholson, Jeffrey J. Iliff, Takahiro Takano, Rashid Deane, Maiken Nedergaard, *Sleep Drives Metabolite Clearance from the Adult Brain* (Science 2013)
35 <https://europepmc.org/backend/ptpmcrender.fcgi?accid=PMC3880190&blobtype=pdf>
81. Aurora D'Atri, Serena Scarpelli, Maurizio Gorgoni, Ilaria Truglia, Giulia Lauri, Susanna Cordone, Michele Ferrara, Camillo Marra⁴, Paolo Maria Rossini, Luigi De Gennaro, *EEG alterations during wake and sleep in mild cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's disease* (iScience 2021)
40 <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8086022/>
82. Anita Pal, Nishi Pegwal, Madhuri Behari, Ratna Sharma, *High delta and gamma EEG power in resting state characterise dementia in Parkinson's patients* (Biomarkers in Neuropsychiatry 2020)
45 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666144620300174>

Footnotes – Continued

5 83. Juliane Bjerkan, Jan Kobal, Gemma Lancaster, Sanja Šešok, Bernard Meglič, Peter V. E. McClintock, Karol P. Budohoski, Peter J. Kirkpatrick, Aneta Stefanovska, *The phase coherence of the neurovascular unit is reduced in Huntington’s disease* (Brain Communications 2024)

<https://academic.oup.com/braincomms/article/6/3/fcae166/7689585>

10 84. Morteza Abyadeh, Vivek Gupta, Joao A. Paulo, Arezoo Gohari Mahmoudabad, Sina Shadfar, Shahab Mirshahvaladi, Veer Gupta, Christine T.O. Nguyen, David I. Finkelstein, Yuyi You, Paul A. Haynes, Ghasem H. Salekdeh, Stuart L. Graham, Mehdi Mirzaei, *Amyloid-beta and tau protein beyond Alzheimer’s disease* (Neural Regeneration Research 2024)

15 https://journals.lww.com/nrronline/fulltext/2024/06000/amyloid_beta_and_tau_protein_beyond_alzheimer_s.29.aspx

20 85. Marija Vidović, Milena G. Rikalovic, *Alpha-Synuclein Aggregation Pathway in Parkinson’s Disease: Current Status and Novel Therapeutic Approaches* (Cells 2022)

<https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4409/11/11/1732>

86. Montserrat Arrasate, Steven Finkbeiner, *Protein aggregates in Huntington’s disease* (Experimental Neurology 2014)

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3909772/>